

A review on synthesis and features of different types of Carbon nanostructures deposited by RF-PECVD

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Abstract - This review is about the synthesis of different types of carbon nanostructures by Radio Frequency Plasma Enhanced Chemical vapor deposition (RF-PECVD) and its feasibility to grow variety of carbon nanostructures and their features. A variety of carbon nanostructures like carbon nanosheets, carbon nanoparticles, carbon nanotubes, nanoellipse like structures, nanorods and other islands like carbon nanostructures were grown at possibly low synthesis temperatures was reported at various international and national level journals is a part of my own research work. With the mission of make benefit for the easy understanding of the graduate students, scholars, academicians and researchers, it is presenting as a review report. In this report, first section contains a review on different types of synthesis techniques and their failure in the growth of pure, individual and aligned carbon nanostructures at low synthesis temperatures and the feasibility of RF-PECVD in the growth of carbon nanostructures for full filling the above-mentioned requirements is discussed. Second section deals about the RF-PECVD technic and it's inbuilt facilities for the growth of carbon nanostructures compared to the other techniques. Third section presents about the different types of grown carbon nanostructures during the period of my own research work using RF-PECVD. Fourth section presents about the applications of these carbon nanostructures in various fields.

Keywords – RF-PECVD, Island like carbon nanosheets, Carbon nanorods, Nano ellipse like structures, Carbon nanotubes.

INTRODUCTION

Since the discovery of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [1], these carbon nanostructures have attracted extensive attention in and across the Globe due to their novel properties and potential applications such as high performing nanomaterials, high efficiency energy storage devices, cold field emitters and their use in composite materials [2]. Many methods have been used for fabrication of carbon nanostructures, including arc discharge [3], pulsed laser deposition [4], thermal chemical vapor deposition [5], direct current [6], hot filament chemical vapor deposition and microwave chemical vapor deposition [7], in the methods like Arc discharge, pulsed laser deposition and direct current carbon nanostructures are synthesized by disturbing the graphite target with high energetic laser beam or with high voltage current and collecting the graphite granules is the top-down approach [8] and the carbon nanostructures synthesized by these methods are impure and having wide variety of structures and synthesized at and above 1000o C temperature. Thermal CVD referred above requires high temperature, generally from 800 to 2000 °C, which can be generated by resistance heating, high-frequency induction, radiant heating, hot plate heating, or any combination of these. The produced carbon nanotubes are multi-walled [9], not having defined size and pattern growth. Most of these methods

are operated at high temperatures around 10000C, such high temperatures are not suitable for working, especially with respect to electronics where most components are highly temperature sensitive. Consequently, one of the major hindrances in commercializing carbon nanostructure-based applications is the high temperature for synthesis. For the growth of the individual, positional, density controlled and purified carbon nanostructures, we chose Radio Frequency Plasma Enhanced Chemical Vapor Deposition (RF-PECVD) equipped with the arrangements of digitally varied parameters like gas composition, time deposition, synthesis temperature and RF-power.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

Figure 1 represents the RF powered Plasma Enhanced Chemical Vapor Deposition system procured from HIND HIVAC, Bangalore is a PECVD system powered by a 500W RF power source. Pumped by a combination of rotary vane pump, roots booster pump and an oil diffusion pump, a pressure of about 1×10^{-6} mbar can routinely be achieved in the system. Equipped with pirani gauges, a high-resolution digital pirani gauge and penning gauge for measuring vacuum, the system becomes a robust equipment capable of producing reliable results. Feed gases (Argon & Methane) are pumped through

appropriate mass flow controllers for perfect control. Featuring a substrate heater (800 °C), the system is ideal for fabrication of carbon nanotubes, DLC thin films and other carbon nanostructures

Fig. 1 Photograph of HIND HIVAC Radio Frequency PECVD system.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2.1 represents the FE-SEM image of the grown carbon nanostructures on Si substrate, the growth of widely distributed Island-like carbon nanostructures with big size has seen at and around 700 °C. The grown nanostructures are agglomerated in nature and the average diameter of the grown carbon nanostructures is roughly around 65 nm; it is represented by the graph drawn for the particle size distribution as shown in the inset of figure 2.1. By increasing the synthesis temperature, carbon kinetics increases along with Methane dehydrogenation and carbon diffusion. Therefore, both nucleation and growth take very less time, leading to the increase of density as well as the size of the structure.

Fig. 2.1 FE-SEM image of carbon nanostructures grown at 700 °C, the other deposition conditions are 30% Methane, RF-power (500W) and 20 minutes of deposition time.

It is well known that the surface morphology of the carbon nanostructures is important with respect to tribological applications. The three-dimensional AFM image shown in figure 2.2 indicates the growth of the Island-like nanosheets and the large area roughness of the samples. RMS roughness histograms plotted based on these samples indicate that the samples have low roughness of about 0.130nm consistently. This indicates a uniform nanosheet growth over large areas.

Fig. 2.2 AFM 3D image of carbon nanostructures grown at a temperature of 700 °C, the other deposition conditions are 30% Methane, RF- power (500W) and the deposition time of 20 minutes.

Fig. 3.1 AFM image and the corresponding line profile of the Fe thin film deposited on Si (1 0 0) substrate with a thickness of 10 nm by e-beam PVD technique.

Figure 3.1 represents the AFM image of the Fe-catalyst films grown on Si substrate after 60 minutes pre-etching, a good activation behavior of the catalyst film is observed. It is seen that the catalyst film breaks into individual and small granules of size roughly about 100 nm in diameter measured by AFM line profile graph. It can be explained in two ways; due to long time of pre-etching, density of high energetic Ar⁺ ions and electrons in the plasma operates with a high frequency of (13.56 MHz) increases. Mass of the electrons is very less compared to the heavy argon atoms and Ar⁺ ions. Therefore, this lighter electron attains high energy levels more easily than the heavier species and causes the secondary electrons. Hence, it causes the bombardment of a greater number of Ar⁺ ions and electrons in less time, which in turn helps the increment of rate of etching and efficiency of the etching reaction. On the other side, due to long time pre-etching, there must be an increase of the substrate temperature; because of more time etching process of high and concentrated ionic atmosphere.

Fig. 3.2. High magnification FE-SEM images of the carbon nanostructures grown on Si (100) substrate coated with Fe-film with a thickness of 10 nm, after 60 minutes pre-etching

It is believed that nanostructures grown by the decomposition of the carbonaceous gas on the surface of a catalyst granule. The carbon dissolves in the catalyst, diffuses through it, and exits to form the carbon nanostructure. Two –dimensional rod-shaped carbon nano structures were clearly observed from figure 3.2 taken by high magnification mode of FE-SEM. The shape proportionates to the shape of the catalyst granule shown in figure 3.1.

Fig.4. AFM image with corresponding line profile-showing diameter of the nano-ellipse to be around 115nm.

The image in figure 4 shows a novel morphology of carbon nanostructures found on the silicon substrate and its line profile. A Nano ellipse-like structure is visible, which resembles a seed. These structures were concentrated on a particular region of the wafer. These carbon nanostructures are newly found, and their growth mode is yet to be understood. These nanostructures measure approximately 115 nm in diameter.

Fig. 5. FE-SEM images of carbon nanotubes grown on Si (100) substrate coated with SiO₂ oxide layer of a thickness roughly about 50nm followed by Ni catalyst with a thickness of roughly about 5 to 10 nm.

Features observed in the figure 5 represents the carbon nanotubes grown on the SiO₂ coated Ni catalysed substrate, the SiO₂ layer prevent the formation of the Ni-silicate and which intern supports the growth of oriented and lengthy grown carbon nanotubes over the substrate. From figure 5 the length of the grown nanotube is roughly about 2 μm and the length of another nanotube is roughly about 1.5 μm.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A variety of carbon nanostructures including Island-like nanosheets, nanorods, nanoparticles, nanoellipse and nanotubes like structures were synthesized at a very low synthesis temperature. The morphology of the nanostructures

and their growth mode were discussed. Carbon nanostructures with varying morphological configurations have sought the attention of the researchers in recent times. The foundation for their interest lies in the potential applications of these nanostructures from innovative electronics to structural elements. The presence of such properties in these structures is due to the specialized orientation of sp² bonded carbon and the behavior of their electronic structure [10]. These structures hold promise for field emission and catalysts due to their sharp edges, upright orientation and surface area [11, 12]. The inductive coupled plasma of the RF-PECVD proved to be a powerful method for the synthesis of carbon nanostructures at less temperatures, it can be concluded that RF-PECVD is a robust technique to synthesize different types of carbon nanostructures.

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